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FACULTY OF BUILT ENVIRONMENT

DEPARTMENT OF PLANNING

Housing Finance in Slums in the Kumasi Metropolis

By

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A thesis submitted to the Department of Planning, College of Art and Built Environment in
partial fulfillment of the requirement for the degree of a

BACHELOR OF SCIENCE

SEPTEMBER, 2022

DECLARATION

"I hereby declare that I undertook the study described herein under supervision."

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ABSTRACT

All over the world, slum dwellers face difficulties in obtaining funds from the formal sector to build their homes and make improvements to their existing structures. They struggle with this problem mainly because people who live in slums typically have low incomes and unstable land tenure, among other things. This study's main goal was to investigate additional creative approaches to financing slum housing.

To conduct the study, questionnaires had to be distributed in the target area (Aboabo). This was done to help the researcher comprehend the socioeconomic makeup of the local population and their housing conditions, as well as to find opportunities and limitations for obtaining financing. To pinpoint the main issues in the community, leaders in the community were additionally questioned. Additionally, interviews with representatives of pertinent institutions (GWCL, PPD, ECG, AMMA, etc.) were conducted to comprehend institutional efforts to better the living conditions of Kumasi's slum dwellers.

According to the study, housing conditions in Aboabo are generally poor, with rusty and leaking roofs, exposed foundations, poor drainage, inadequate sanitary facilities, and poor garbage collection. Respondents were mostly self-employed and had little formal education. In terms of housing finance, the study found that the majority of residents used their own money to fund home improvements and construction. The study also found that residents prefer to use their resources (equity finance) to evaluate loans, particularly those from banks (debt finance). The study revealed that the inhabitants had a culture of saving. Respondents expressed an interest in taking part in financing schemes.

The study recommends that local Susu companies be regulated to provide the best services to slum dwellers. The study also suggests that individual Susu companies merge to create greater leverage in terms of contributors' access to finance.

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ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

With the kind assistance and support of many people, this thesis is made a reality. I want to express my heartfelt gratitude to each and every one of them.

First and foremost, I want to express my profound appreciation to the Almighty God, who has kindly provided me with the strength and knowledge to finish this academic endeavour.

I would like to thank my mentor and supervisor, Mr. Prince Anokye Aboagye, for his constant guidance and inspiration throughout this program of my bachelor's studies. The cordial relationship you extended to me gave me a lot of confidence and enthusiasm for the future.

Finally, I really like to express my gratitude to my parents for their unwavering support and understanding while I was conducting research and completing my thesis. Your prayers for me have kept me going thus far.

DEDICATION

This work is the result of many long and difficult sacrifices. This work is cheerfully and proudly dedicated to the people who serve as inspiration via the research endeavor. From my parents to my classmates and circle of friends, everyone pitched in to help when things became tough while undertaking this project.

To the whole academic staff of Kwame Nkrumah University of Science and Technology's Department of Planning. Above all, I am grateful to my God Almighty for showering me with His blessings in my daily life, especially for the strength, courage, patience, wisdom, time, and direction in completing this project.

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

AMMA	Asokore Mampong Municipal Assembly
ECG	Electricity Company of Ghana
GSS	Ghana Statistical Service
GWCL	Ghana Water Company Limited
KENSUP	Kenya Slum Upgrading Programme
KMA	Kumasi Metropolitan Assembly
MDG	Millennium Development Goal
PPD	Physical Planning Department

CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background of Study

The problem of slum expansion is a matter of global concern. Millennium Development Goal (MDG) 7, Goal 11, calls for the lives of at least 100 million slum residents to be significantly improved by 2020 by reducing poverty and improving water and sanitation. According to UN HABITAT (2006), slums are home to 72% of the urban population of sub-Saharan Africa, 59% of the urban population of South Asia, and 32% of the urban population of Latin America.

This phenomenon is not exclusive to Ghana. These slums, which are mostly built without planning authorization, have resulted in a lack of essential social services in the areas where they are found. People who live in these neighborhoods face the worst living and environmental conditions and are isolated from the city's economic, social, political, and cultural realms (Arimah, undated). People who do not have access to such fundamental conveniences do not live-in comfort.

Slum dwellers' socioeconomic position is mostly defined by low income and a lack of education (Akteer, undated). 'The repercussions of increasing urbanization are already visible in metropolitan Ghana, manifesting in socio-economic, environmental, and institutional issues for urban people and local governments (Owusu and Afutu-Kotey, 2010). Location, density, building quality, size, and amount of consolidation all differ among slums. Slum inhabitants, on the other hand, share some common characteristics, such as a lack of access to basic infrastructure and land-owning issues, which negatively affect slum dwellers' health and general well-being. These negative consequences include an increase in social vices like robbery, prostitution, and sexual abuse, as well as diseases like cholera.

Slums are not just a current occurrence; they will continue to exist in the future. As a result, adequate attention must be paid to improving the lives of potential slum dwellers. There have been numerous studies and efforts aimed at improving and removing slums. Despite several efforts to investigate slum repair and elimination, the situation remains unchanged. This research aims to determine how slum conditions can be changed to improve the living conditions of individuals who already reside there through housing finance.

1.2 Problem Statement

According to Article 11 of the International Covenant on Economic, Social, and Cultural Rights, having adequate housing is a fundamental human right (UN, 1966). The term "housing" refers to both the physical structure of the home as well as the amenities and services required to enjoy it. According to (Okewole and Aribigbola, 2006) as mentioned in Lanrewaju (2012), housing quality refers to a variety of characteristics such as the physical condition of the building as well as various amenities and amenities services that make living in a certain region comfortable. Housing in every community should be of sufficient quality to meet minimal health and living standards while remaining affordable to all types of households. Slum inhabitants, according to Dudhwala (2012), experience terrible housing conditions.

The World Bank performed research in Nairobi slums in 2006 and found that slum populations prioritize home quality improvement (World Bank 2006). This suggests that slum inhabitants want to better their living situations. Despite the need to improve slum housing, several scholars have found that housing finance is a significant barrier to improving housing conditions for the urban poor. Part of the reason for this is the economic condition of slum inhabitants, who are frequently in the low-income category (Dinye and Acheampong, 2013). Because of their low income, they are unable to obtain official financing. "...slum residents are frequently systematically barred from the so-called 'formal' system of housing finance, particularly mortgage finance," according to (FIG/UN-HABITAT, 2008; pg. 15). Banks are bound by the credit risk analysis methods they deploy, which include financial, legal, and technical systems. Financial analysts prefer those with a bank account, formal work, and proven credit history. During their forensic investigations, financial institutions look for evidence of acceptable legal title and the ability to recover assets in court in the event of default. Based on their technical investigation, they will also look for evidence of building permits and compliance with zoning regulations. The formal market test of poor credit failed all three risk analysis procedures.

Furthermore, according to a 2004 World Bank report, there is a lack of financial commitment to upgrading slum living conditions, and the local government lacks the financial resources to shoulder such costs.

As a result, this research aims to look at additional innovative ways of funding housing in slums other than the official sector, which slum inhabitants are unable to access so that they can experience high-quality living circumstances that affect their overall well-being.

1.3 Study Objectives

The study's overall goal is to find and examine finance options for improving housing conditions in slum areas within the Kumasi Metropolitan Area. The study also intends to make policy recommendations to solve the issues that have been highlighted.

The study aims to accomplish the following goals in particular.

- To investigate the characteristics of housing and living situations.
- Identifying and analyzing funding sources for slum house improvement
- To investigate the housing financing possibilities for slum inhabitants.
- To provide recommendations to city officials on potential possibilities for improving slum inhabitants' housing conditions.

1.4 Research Questions

- What are the housing characteristics and living situations of slums in the Kumasi Metropolis?
- What are the funding sources for slum house improvement?
- What are the housing financing possibilities for slum inhabitants in the Kumasi Metropolis?

1.5 Scope of Study

The current housing conditions in slums will be examined in this study, which will be supported by alternative financial choices in the study region. This research will look into the financial possibilities for housing improvements in slum neighborhoods in the Kumasi Metropolis. Geographically, the study focuses on the Kumasi Metropolitan Area in Ghana's Ashanti Region of the Republic of Ghana.

1.6 Significance of Study

The majority of the literature focuses on ways to rehabilitate slum neighborhoods. As a result, this study will disclose slum housing circumstances and issues that have evolved as a result of local

and international institutions' efforts to improve slum housing conditions. We will be able to create a meaningful structure to enhance housing conditions in slum regions in this way.

This research will provide the planning authority with raw data on slum regions and the issues that residents in these areas encounter. This will assist them in determining the most effective approaches to enhance these areas.

This report will also be required by the government to strengthen slum improvement policies. This study has the potential to be the breakthrough that the government needs to help transform the awful status of slums.

In addition to learning about residents' difficulties in financing housing improvements in slum regions, we will be able to determine the residents' attitudes toward change. The study will also analyze how likely people in slum areas are to accept environments with better conditions than the ones in which they currently reside.

This research will contribute to the corpus of information that will help the nation create future slum improvement initiatives.

1.7 Summary of Methodology

This study employed a mixed methodology that included quantitative and qualitative research methods. The term "mixed method" refers to a research approach that incorporates both philosophical assumptions and scientific exploratory methods. The study included both primary and secondary sources of data. Because it makes use of both, the study is reliable (Patton, 1990). The majority of the questionnaires, which were given personally to selected homes and professionals, were used to collect data from inhabitants. Interviews were also done inside the ministries.

1.8 Data Requirements and Sources

To conduct a successful study, the researchers needed information from the community's residents, leaders, and relevant institutions. The social, physical, economic, and housing characteristics of the study area, as well as the financial options available for housing finance, were required pieces of information. A list of all the information gathered for the study, along with its sources, can be found below.

TYPE OF DATA	SOURCES
A review of the literature on slum housing finance	Department of Planning Library and Main Library of KNUST, Internet resources from UN, World Bank, and works of individuals
Maps of Kumasi and the study area	ArcGIS
Information on slum dwellers' socioeconomic characteristics, housing conditions, and housing financing options	Landlords, landladies, or caretakers of houses in Aboabo
Aboabo's housing needs and the challenges of improving housing conditions	Community leaders
Major projects undertaken in Aboabo to improve water supply, as well as the challenges encountered	Ghana Water Company Limited (GWCL)
Major projects undertaken in Aboabo to improve electricity supply and the challenges encountered	Electricity Company of Ghana (ECG)
Aboabo is undertaking major projects to improve waste management and disposal	Waste Management Department of KMA

Sources: Author's Construct (2022)

1.9 Limitations of the Study

Several obstacles were faced over the course of the study, such as the unwillingness of slum residents and organizations to provide the researcher with information. Nevertheless, the researcher approached this by using introductory letters and interacting with local leaders in the study area to legitimize the study. The respondents were fluent in local languages (Twi and Hausa), with relatively few fluent in English, which jeopardized the study's progress because the researcher was unfamiliar with the languages spoken.

1.10 Terms Explained

Urbanization - The process by which large groups of populations concentrate permanently on relatively limited areas that eventually form cities is known as urbanization. Internal rural to urban migration describes emigration from smaller to larger towns. As a result, the population density of those living in cities increases relative to those in smaller towns and their suburbs. Thus, if the rate of natural population growth in cities exceeds that in rural areas, an increase in urbanization may naturally take place. This kind of situation doesn't happen very often. According to Long (1998), 50% of a nation's people must reside in its major cities for that nation to be deemed urbanized.

Urban area - An urban area is defined as a settlement with a population of more than 5000 people that has modern amenities such as electricity, schools, and some industries (the 2000 population and housing census of Ghana).

Population growth - Population growth is the increase in the population of a particular territory, such as a nation, state, or city (UNFPA, 2007).

Housing deficit - This is a reference to the lack of housing units necessary to accommodate the local population in a given area (BoG, 2007).

Affordable housing - This outlines the housing system suitable for a range of moderately priced to low-income households and priced so that these family units can also afford other essential living expenses like food, clothing, transportation, and medical care. Housing is generally considered affordable if the costs are less than 30% of the gross household income.

Access to housing - The availability of housing units that can accommodate the entire population of an area is referred to as accessibility. The "ability to access" and reap the benefits of a specific system, in this case, housing, is another way to view accessibility (MWRWH, 2009).

Slum - A slum is a heavily populated area with subpar living conditions. According to UNHABITAT 2011, a slum is a decrepit area of a city that is distinguished by substandard housing, filth, and the need for tenure security.

1.11 Organization of the Study

The first chapter introduces and contextualizes the study, as well as the problem statement and study objectives. The study's research questions, scope, justification, and limitations are also examined.

The second chapter examines the literature on low-income populations and slum housing financing approaches in developing countries. The third chapter discusses the research techniques and methodology. The fourth chapter contains survey findings and data analysis. The study's findings, recommendations, and conclusion are reported in chapter five.

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Introduction

This chapter reviews the pertinent literature on informal settlements (slums, shanty towns, and squatter settlements), as well as information on the idea of unauthorized structures, types of informal settlements, their characteristics, the historical development of unauthorized structures, factors influencing their expansion, and financing options for slum housing improvements. This chapter discusses government initiatives as well as a case study of creative financing for slum housing in another nation.

2.2 The Concept of Unauthorized Structures

When discussing unlawful constructions, the words "slum" and "squatter" settlements come to mind. Slums, according to The Global Development Research Centre (2003), are densely populated urban regions characterized by degraded unlawful and unsanitary structures, poverty, and social disarray. The environment of a place with a majority of disadvantaged residents is described by the name "slum" (UN-Habitat, 1982; 1987). The following features of slum buildings have been identified by Devadas and Desai (1990):

- They are in a damaged, deteriorated, and old state; and
- In terms of ventilation, lighting, and sanitation, they are woefully underserved.

Slums, according to Devadas and Desai (1990), are found in the following places:

- a scarcity of open areas and recreational facilities
- congested and heavily inhabited
- they are also poorly planned for sanitation, safety, and other physical infrastructure; and, ultimately, they are distinguished by
- faulty or insufficient roadway and lot layouts

These traits suggest poor health and provide an arena for social vices. Squatting is the unlawful occupancy of private or public property without authorization or valid legal grounds. Squatters are people or small groups that invade a space, sometimes as a result of coordinated activity. A specific location where squatters live is known as a "squatter area" (Devadas & Desai, 1990).

Squatter settlements are given different names based on their development type, according to UN-Habitat (1987). For example, squatter colonies that emerged due to a lack of central or local government finances and institutional planning or development control are often referred to as "spontaneous settlements." When such communities don't have official registration or aren't in compliance with regulations, the phrase "uncontrolled settlements" is used. Squatter communities are commonly referred to as "shantytowns" due to their inferior structure. Squatter communities are sometimes referred to as "popular settlements" since they primarily comprise low-income earners. Squatter communities are also referred to as "marginal settlements" due to their lower social and economic contributions to urban society. The term "transitional settlement" is occasionally used to refer to the area where squatters live since they frequently combine their positions and reside permanently in the city (UN-Habitat, 1987).

The phrase "informal settlement" has recently been used to describe all slums and squatter settlements (Devadas & Desai, 1990); they are made up of numerous illegal structures and represent a situation where a significant number of people (especially the urban disadvantaged) earn or seek to earn their living. These locations frequently feature densely populated areas where people live in independently built homes that were created using standard blueprints. All slums and squatter colonies are categorized as "unauthorized" in this study.

2.3 Types of Informal Settlements

The United Nations Economic Commission for Europe [UNECE] categorizes informal settlements into five (5) main types, which are as follows:

- Upgraded squatter settlement: This kind of community typically begins as a squatter community and develops into an established neighborhood. They frequently achieve de facto legality. When governments supply certain amenities, homes may develop into thriving rental and homeownership markets;
- Subdivision without authorization: This type of informal community is typically constructed on the unlawful property without a planning or building permit. Even though the village may not be of high quality, some residents may have land titles. Such communities are prohibited because they contravene land-use planning and may have subpar facilities that don't adhere to building safety regulations. In the long run, nonetheless, they are frequently accepted and may be included in master plans;

- Settlement for internally displaced people and vulnerable groups of refugees: This kind of settlement is typically created with the government's approval as a temporary reaction to a catastrophe. These settlements are typically located near refugee camps, in marginal areas of cities, or on the outskirts of urban areas. Living conditions are poor, and displaced populations encounter major challenges that hinder their ability to return home or integrate locally;
- Substandard inner-city housing: This comprises congested, decrepit housing in city centers or densely urbanized areas that lacks basic facilities. The sites were originally developed and designed, but as a result of chronic underinvestment, they have steadily lost their attractiveness and quality over time. Security of tenure may not be an issue, but the safety and quality of housing should be considered; and
- Squatter settlements: These are urban areas where people who have illegally occupied a piece of land have built their homes using do-it-yourself techniques. They frequently follow sudden influxes of people into towns and cities. The least desirable sort of dwelling, slums frequently lack running water and proper sanitation. In some circumstances, unstable terrain puts locals in grave danger. Additionally, residents frequently experience social marginalization and segregation.

2.4 Characteristics of Unauthorized Structures

Unauthorized buildings can be categorized into various forms. Nawagamuwa and Viking (2003) state that an unlawful structure in an informal settlement might be an improvised structure built of cardboard, plastic sheets, rags, tin sheets, clay, adobe, thatch, and wood scraps (sticks, barks, and leaves, for example). This type of civilization includes caves that have been excavated from hillsides and empty carts. People live in floating squatter colonies in several South-East Asian nations, such as Vietnam, on junks or other boats (Nawagamuwa & Viking, 2003).

The single-story varieties of illegal structures, particularly residences, fall under other classifications. However, as noted by Desai and Devadas (1990), six-story buildings can be found. Many of the structures here lack windows, making it impossible for residents to see one another without a light source or fire even during the day. Lack of fresh air flow and insufficient ventilation is also a problem. The living room, bedroom, ward, kitchen, and dining room are often combined into one space. It is not uncommon for more than four to ten people to share a room.

According to Nawagamuwa and Viking (2003), the following are some of the most essential characteristics of unauthorized structures in informal settlements:

- structures, yards, and streets that are inadequately built and maintained;
- poor-income earners; low-income households typically work as wage laborers or in various informal sector firms. The household income level might be quite high at times;
- overpopulation; either the area is overloaded with buildings, or the buildings are overcrowded with inhabitants, or both;
- diverse population; Many people can't afford to live in posh neighborhoods or neighborhoods, so homes are occupied by the elderly, those with chronic illnesses, and the socially awkward.
- the inhabitants' unemployment rate is considerable; yet, Melese (2006) discovered that dwellers in unlawful structures are not unemployed, but rather self-employed because of their poor educational level.
- the neighborhood has a relatively low level of cleanliness, which contributes to illness outbreaks and high death rates; and
- because social vices predominate, all sites may not contain "successful" criminals, but they may serve as their hiding places.

2.4.1 Building Materials

Urban dwellers around the world struggle to find durable building materials, according to estimates from UN-Habitat (2006a). Slum areas are known for having a large number of subpar housing structures that are frequently made of temporary materials that are unsuitable for housing given the local climate and geography (Global Report on Human Settlements, 2003). Buildings in slum areas frequently do not meet the specifications and standards set by city officials for residential structures. Earthen floors, mud-and-wattle walls, or straw roofs, for example, are listed as contributing factors in the Global Report on Human Settlements from 2003. Slum-dwellers construct their homes using subpar building materials, recycled materials, or other methods that fall far short of industry standards, such as cardboard, fabric, scrap metal, tables, or other structures. Additionally, these inferior building materials are used in frequently unlawful home additions.

The majority of slum dwellers' ability to buy standardized building materials is influenced by their financial situation. As a result, they frequently carry out developments using materials that are easily accessible in their surroundings. According to a 2004 study done in Accra, Ghana, many homes were built of wood or other temporary materials and were situated on marginal lands (Malcom and Braimah, 2004). According to the study, 58 percent of Accra's population resided in low-lying, flood-prone areas like Korle-Gonno. Ninety-eight (98%) percent of the homes in this settlement had wooden construction, which increased the risk of fire outbreaks.

2.4.2 Conditions for Land Tenure

Not all slum dwellers, unlike squatters, are illegally residing there; however, typically, a large number of slum dwellers live in fear of being forcibly evicted or transferred to unsuitable locations (Malcom and Braimah, 2004). According to a 2008 World Bank study, slum dwellers are forced to occupy insecure lands, and this unauthorized land acquisition fosters instability and vulnerability. Slum-dwellers who lease buildings in slums frequently discover a lack of documentation in the form of leases to protect their interests. This may be caused by the average low level of education among slum dwellers.

Slum-dwellers in Ghana face challenges related to the price of purchasing land and acquiring a good title. The process of perfecting a title involves physical inspection, a search at the Lands Commission to look up records of previous and current owners, as well as other administrative procedures. It is a capital-constricting procedure.

2.4.3 Housing Facilities

There are three different kinds of physical services for housing, according to the World Bank (2008). The services can be categorized as on-plot, on-site, or off-site. Private use restrooms, electricity, and water are available as on-site services. Footpaths, street lighting, and public amenities like waste collection are examples of on-site services that are utilized by a group of residents. Facilities that are utilized by site residents, as well as the entire city, are considered off-site services. Examples include access to main roads, water pipelines, infrastructure network services, and public electrification (World Bank, 2008).

The inaccessibility of water and sanitation services is allegedly one of the traits of slums (Dubbale and Tsutsami, 2010). It is either impossible to obtain or very difficult to obtain formal service

providers' access to utilities like water, electricity, and sanitary facilities. They must therefore find alternative sources of electricity as well as purchase water from vendors (Malcom and Braimah, 2004).

Well-constructed roads and walkways define formal settlements. Slums, on the other hand, are distinguished by access routes that are typically small and challenging to access because of the high density of improperly planned structures. Normally, footpaths are used to enter settlements, but doing so puts households at greater risk of flooding or fire outbreaks (Malcom and Braimah, 2004).

2.4.4 Housing Environment

Slums have terrible sanitation. Few people have access to bathrooms or sewers, therefore inhabitants frequently use "flying toilets," which are just plastic bags filled with human waste that are tossed down drains and other communal areas. Though they occasionally aren't allowed to, some locals assert that they use the restrooms at the local church and bars (Karanja and Makau, Undated).

Ayigya, Kumasi's slum had exposed building foundations as a result of erosion brought on by rains, according to Dinye and Acheampong (2013). The foundations of the houses were exposed as a result of the runoff since there were insufficient drains to direct the water. Additionally, because the majority of the houses had additions (attachments), it was essential for the builder to dig into the foundation of the old building before joining it with the attached building, which made the foundation more susceptible to erosion. A lot of slums are in a similar condition to this one.

2.5 Factors that Contribute to the Development of Unlawful Structures

According to the United Nations (UN) (2007), population shifts that cause armed conflicts, urbanization-related political and socioeconomic situations, and fatal natural disasters are the main causes of the formation of unauthorized constructions. According to the UN (2007), institutional, physical, and cultural variables all have a role in the development of unauthorized constructions in urban areas.

Political factors

Inadequate housing policies of governments to provide affordable housing projects for the poor and middle-income earners, along with political instability, are what, according to the United Nations (2007), led to the proliferation of unauthorized constructions. According to Kombe and Kreibich (2000), Tanzania's government's failure to address the housing requirements of the underprivileged has led those living in poverty to find creative ways to build homes, leading to the emergence of numerous illegal buildings in Tanzanian cities. Unlawful structure expansion is also significantly influenced by the lack of political will on the part of the government to stop it. The UN-Habitat (2003) research demonstrates that governments' lack of political will to enact laws intended to prevent the proliferation of unauthorized structures is a factor contributing to the growth of such structures (Warah, 2003).

Socio-economic factors

According to Sietchiping (2000), the reasons for the prevalence of unlawful constructions in emerging nations include high land prices and rent in urban areas, large immigration rates, issues with landlessness, poverty, and unemployment. In Port Harcourt, Nigeria, Kings-Amadi (2004) noted that unpermitted structures resulted from a lack of public education or awareness of planning regulations, land users' ignorance, their unwillingness to accept established regulations, and the high cost (of money) associated with obtaining the proper land papers. One of the socioeconomic elements that affect the growth of unlawful constructions, according to Augustijn, Flacke, and Iqbal (2009), is social ties or relationships.

Physical factors

The development of shanty towns may be influenced by the geographic location and physical characteristics (land characteristics) of cities and urban areas. Most people prefer residing in convenient locations close to their places of employment, infrastructure, and urban amenities, particularly those related to health and education (Magalhaes & Eduardo, 2007). Urban areas are seen as venues by millions of poor individuals in emerging nations to raise their standard of living. The city center is a "destination of choice" because it offers more access to paid employment, more diverse foods, higher education, and better health care. This circumstance has led to significant migration to cities in contrast to the perceived backwardness and poverty in rural areas (Nawagamuwa & Viking, 2003). Some people choose to live in marginal territories that are

ignored by city officials. The deep valleys in Kenya, the river banks in Bombay, the abandoned rubbish dumps in Manila, and the treacherous slopes in Yaoundé are just a few examples of cheap, vulnerable, and undeveloped metropolitan places where unauthorized structures can be discovered.

Cultural factors

The spread of unlawful constructions is significantly influenced by culture (Ali & Sulaiman, 2006). Due mostly to their culture, many urban residents of Zanzibar feel very at home in slum neighborhoods and think that these are the only places where they may experience "Swahili life" (that is sharing, and togetherness among relatives). They believe that settlements with good infrastructure and services, such as those in Mombasa, Mbweni, and Mazzini (where residents erect tall fences around their homes), are only appropriate for those with large incomes or Uzunguni (the rich). Some of these locations are known as "masikini hajengi" (that is the poor cannot afford to build). There is no question regarding the "legality" of the occupants' homes in their thoughts (Ali & Sulaiman, 2006). According to surveys on illegal structures conducted by Ali and Sulaiman (2006), security of tenure was generally not seen as a problem. Once a house was constructed, one could claim ownership of the land and there was hardly any chance of being evicted from the neighborhood.

According to Augustijn et al. (2009), many conventional systems particularly marriage, security concerns, and family ties encourage the establishment of slums. Other studies (Berg-Schlusser & Kersting, 2003; Davis, 2004) contend that spiritual or religious practices play a role in the development of slums, at least in part. For new urban migrants who favor settling in communities with comparable religious (cultural) backgrounds, such a correlation is extensively documented (Malpezzi & SaAdu, 1996).

2.6 Definition of Low Income Groups

The term "urban poor" is most frequently used to describe low-income urban groups. Yeboah (2005) asserts that in both academic and professional contexts, including those of the United Nations and national governments, the terms "low-income" and "the poor" are interchangeable. Yeboah points out that although it may not be the most accurate way to measure poverty, the lack of distinction between poverty and low income is based on this presumption. The low-income population has essentially no standardized definition. A household daily income of \$1 or less per

day is the tacit definition that is most frequently used in poverty literature and that local financial intermediaries have adopted. According to the Ghana Statistical Service (GSS), the lower and upper poverty lines are respectively estimated at GH288.47 and GH370.89 per adult per year. In Ghana, this serves as the starting point when discussing income levels. These poverty thresholds are based on dietary intake. The GSS classifies consumers above the poverty line as non-poor (Ghana Statistical Service, 2007).

UN-Habitat describes three main characteristics of poverty: poor in money, poor in access, and poor in power (2009). When urban poor people do not have enough money to pay for housing and other necessities, they are said to be experiencing financial poverty. Poverty can be further examined from an income perspective within the context of material poverty. There are thus two fundamental categories of poverty, absolute poverty and relative poverty when viewed from this perspective. The price of the bare necessities required to support human life is considered to be the definition of absolute poverty. Globally, this minimum is thought to be \$1 per day. Contrarily, relative poverty is defined as having only the bare minimum of the economic, social, political, and other necessities to maintain a respectable standard of living in a particular society. The poverty of access refers to a lack of access to key infrastructure and services.

There is a wide range of urban poor people in different cities, nations, and even different regions. Urban poverty has many different manifestations and is multidimensional with intricate causal and interactive relationships. According to Baker (2008), the urban poor experience a variety of common deprived conditions that have an impact on their daily lives. These include: insufficient and unstable living conditions, ii) poor infrastructure and services, iii) inadequate and unsafe living conditions, iv) vulnerability to risks like natural disasters, environmental hazards, and health risks, particularly those associated with living in slums, v) spatial issues that impede mobility and transport, and vi) inequality closely related to issues of exclusion.

Because of this, low-income is used widely in this study to refer to both groups or families with consumption levels between the upper poverty line and the non-poor who commonly are excluded from the land and housing markets as a result of the intense competition brought about by market forces. According to this definition, low-income people are restricted to particular settlements in urban areas or cities because of things like price levels, the degree to which land has been

commodified and marketed, and the expense of living in high-density areas without adequate infrastructure and services.

Miltin (2005) suggests that regional size and range of activities are related to economic opportunities in urban areas, and these opportunities increase with location type. Where the low-income groups reside is determined by the spatial dynamics of the city or urban area. As a result, low-income residents of some cities and urban areas may reside in unofficial or illegal neighborhoods in either inner-city or peri-urban areas. The trade-off between land cost and economic opportunities heavily influences which of these locations is chosen. Low-income groups may be able to find affordable housing in peri-urban areas that they can obtain formally from land owners, but these groups frequently face difficulties due to insufficient services and accessible transportation. On the other hand, although inner-city areas may have high service levels, the biggest problems there are high land prices and overcrowding (Miltin, 2005). A typical low-income household in Ghana will therefore lack financial resources, assets, housing, power, and even social networks and capital, but they can still build on peri-urban land using self-help techniques to meet their housing needs.

2.7 Overview of Ghana's Housing

Housing is a problem for all Ghanaians. Urban housing in Ghana is relatively poor in terms of room occupancy and poor condition of structures compared to other African countries (UNHABITAT, 2010). The main players in Ghana's housing market are private developers, individuals, the Ghana government, and numerous non-profit organizations. NGOs such as UNHABITAT and Shelter for Humanity have focused on housing, particularly in rural Ghana (UNHABITAT, 2011; UNHABITAT, 2010). However, the majority of people are responsible for building urban housing with little support from the government or commercial or private developers.

However, the government has always supported the housing industry. Before independence, the British-run government received financial support from the federal government for its housing programs. These housing programs were primarily implemented by the Department of Social Welfare and Housing (DSWH). Between 1946 and 1948, the agency handled the construction of seven funded estate homes in Accra, Takoradi, and Kumasi. Only the urban populace, military

veterans, civil workers, and colonial administrators were given access to these properties. The majority of low-income families outside of urban centers did not benefit from these programs.

By 1982, only 10% of all homes delivered in the country were public housing units, financed by the government with internal and external funds, as opposed to 80% by private developers. Figures show that as of 2006, 90% of the country's housing stock consisted of single-family homes (Kwofie et al., 2011). Since the 1980s, there hasn't been a problem with the government's involvement. The successive governments' planned housing initiatives have either been shelved or never even got off the ground. In 1982, private developers made up 5.5% on average. This performance can only be explained by the nation-economic state's crisis at the time. But later on, private developers increased their ownership to roughly 8%.

Over the past ten years, the government's involvement in housing has been quite low. The fact that none of the government of Ghana's Affordable Housing initiatives from 2001 to 2008 were ever finished serves as evidence of this. Poor planning, a final lack of funding, logistical challenges, and disputes have frequently resulted in the regrettable abandonment of projects that were about to be started or even ones that were halfway through completion. The Government's Affordable Housing Scheme and the STX Housing Project are two recent examples of such failures. Both projects failed mostly owing to financial constraints as well as management and administrative disputes, which can be attributed to incidents. As a result, it is simple to state, both in the absence of context and with the benefit of hindsight, that the government has not made any contributions to housing over the previous ten years, and that Ghana does not have a separate ministry solely responsible for this issue. It is safe to say that the government hasn't actively participated in housing delivery over the past three decades.

As a result of increased rural-urban migration and growth in the urban population, there is a housing scarcity in the nation's largest cities. Perhaps the unexpected drop in supplies is to blame for the scarcity, which has led to an increase in slums and squatter communities (Songsore, 2009; Kwofie et al., 2011). The formerly common compound homes that housed families are no longer being constructed. Urban inhabitants in the country occupy rooms in a variety of multi-occupied residential facilities. Houses in metropolitan areas are typically erected without the approval of the local government and are thus categorized as informal. These illegal structures account for almost 90% of all builds (UNHABITAT, 2011). Again, these buildings are classified as inadequate by

building classification techniques because of a lack of access to proper water, light, and sanitary amenities.

2.8 Housing Finance Techniques

When it comes to housing developments in slum regions, finances are a crucial aspect that must be properly considered. Given the socioeconomic group that slum inhabitants belong to, this cannot be undervalued. Few funding options exist that allow slum residents to design or implement housing projects according to their financial capabilities. The following examines these financing models.

2.8.1 Susu Account

This is one of the continents of Africa's earliest banking systems. To participate in this financial system, community members or interested parties must pay a collector, who then holds their deposits in trust for them. These payments to the collectors are routine and typically of low value. For the contributor, these recurring payments result in significant lump sums that can be utilized to finance housing projects in the future.

This financial arrangement is very practical and exhibits little transaction activity. Zenere (2013) claims that the Susu system eliminates many of the transaction expenses related to working with traditional financial institutions. This technique avoids fees related to the conventional banking system. The Susu story does, however, have some flaws. Contributors are in danger because of the lack of formality, and there have been occasions where Susu collectors have fled with depositors' painstakingly amassed cash.

2.8.2 Cooperative Unions

An independent organization of individuals joined voluntarily to address their shared social-economic, cultural, and aspirational needs through a jointly-owned and democratically-controlled firm are referred to as a cooperative society (UN, 2010). To give everyone access to the capitalist system, credit unions have demonstrated their ability to adjust to shifting economic situations by establishing themselves as sources of economic opportunity (Cobb, 2004). The fundamental idea behind the collaboration is that people work together to accomplish something they cannot do individually. This program can be used to finance slum housing developments (cooperative unions). Cooperative unions, by USAID (2007), guarantee that members can enhance or provide

housing by advocating on their behalf to get land and housing infrastructure, enhancing access to financing, and offering or engaging in technical construction services. It is impossible to undervalue the role that cooperatives play. The HABITAT Agenda's paragraph 56 establishes cooperative societies as local stakeholders who contribute to and support government initiatives to address the needs of the populace in housing. It is crucial to note that there are several issues with this funding model, including the shortage of affordable land, the technical know-how of local operators, and a lack of appropriate financial resources (Lopez, 2010).

2.8.3 Community-Based Shelter Funds

Both settlement improvement and new construction have benefited from community-based financing of housing and services (UN Habitat, 2005). The same source claims that community funds are financial tools that promote saving by forming and supporting neighborhood savings organizations that pool money for housing upgrades. International organizations and funders largely approve of this financing plan (World Bank, 2008). The success and effectiveness of community-based shelter funds as a method of home financing have been established. India, South Africa, and the Philippines have all seen success with it. It can only be successful in areas where there is community participation, as well as where there is a willingness on the part of international organizations and other funding bodies to assist housing initiatives in slum communities.

2.8.4 Loans

The central government was heavily involved in the housing finance system. This involvement includes funding private secondary mortgage market organizations, developing policies to encourage or compel financial institutions to provide housing resources, assisting banking organizations that specialize in housing financing, providing mortgage coverage and This includes providing insurance and possibly securing financing for homebuyers (Carliner, 1998).

2.8.5 Housing Programs

Since the central administration began to express significant worry about this activity in the year 1937, the U.S. has implemented several programs aimed at reducing the cost of housing for low-income individuals. There are numerous schemes that each have an average number of choices, each of which results in a new program that abides by the regulations of the scheme (Olsen, 2003).

2.9 Government Interventions and Policies on Slums

Governments in developing nations have taken conscious efforts and implemented measures to combat the threat of slums (Amoako & Cobbinah, 2011). Below is a discussion of some initiatives and policies that have changed over time.

According to Amoako & Cobbinah (2011), slums were considered to be unlawful between the 1950s and 1960s. However, it was thought that they might be controlled by efficient management by city officials, therefore social housing was offered. Due to the high expense of housing during this period as well as the lack of social results, slums developed (Simpson, 2013). Rural-urban drift increased as a result of the widespread availability of social housing. Rural residents wished to take advantage of the amenities and social housing programs offered in urban areas. Public housing and facilities came under pressure as a result. This policy was unsustainable because project management was tainted by corruption, which worsened the slum situation rather than improved it.

The "Site and Services Approach" helped define the 1970s. This strategy favored the delivery of fundamental services, stable land tenure, creative financial access, and the involvement of slum residents in the process of slum redevelopment. This strategy aimed to give the least fortunate whatever they needed to take care of themselves. This approach needs political will, enhanced local governance, capacity building, as well as cooperation from the government and the community, according to Amoako & Cobbinah (2011). Sadly, this idea also failed since slum inhabitants couldn't afford to provide their housing because of the huge expense required.

As stated, (by Amoako & Cobbinah, 2011), Zwane and Kremer (2007) claim that the 1980s featured slum programs aimed at providing utilities like water and power as well as facilities like roads and streets lights, sewage facilities, and others. The lack of urban services, inadequate infrastructure maintenance, and a lack of community ownership, according to the authors, meant that this approach could not continue. Additionally, organizations involved in this strategy shifted away from devoting a significant portion of resources to this program (World Bank, 2008).

“Property security and ease of dealing with slums” were the hallmarks of the 1990s. This policy attempted to include slum residents in the process of slum upgrading. The goal of this policy was to provide slum inhabitants with legal titles. The decision-making process was coordinated by this

policy with all parties involved. Additionally, it planned to offer serviced land and persuade slum inhabitants to relocate there. Like the others, this policy was unsuccessful. According to the UN (2003), the failure was due to a lack of local support and commitment, a lack of capacity building, and poor financial advice.

The following policy, which was implemented in the early 2000s, is "Participatory Slum Improvement" (Dakpallah, 2011). The overall goal of this program is to enhance fundamental services including health care, education, and interest rates for home development that are affordable. There are some difficulties with this policy. These include a lack of financial support for the policy's financing and political sway.

2.10 Initiatives to Finance the Construction of Slum Housing in Other Nations

Through the funding of housing in these regions, governments and other organizations have undertaken many attempts to improve living conditions in slums. Additionally, slum residents have taken steps to improve their living conditions. By collaborating with donor organizations on slum initiatives, the government has also made the necessary efforts to improve living conditions in slums. In this section, we'll look at two case studies that have started to finance housing development in slum areas.

2.10.1 Case Study Area One: Housing financing in Kenya's Slums (Nairobi)

Kenya's capital city is called Nairobi. In each of Nairobi's eight wards, there are unofficial settlements. Both the demographic makeup and size of these communities vary. According to KENSUP (2012), Nairobi is home to 206 informal communities that together occupy 1,184 hectares of land and house roughly 1,382,205 people. Kibera, Mathare, Korogocho, and Kwa Njenga are the top four informal settlements. Many slum communities were created as a result of the rapid urbanization process and rural-to-urban migration (UN-Habitat, 2003). These slums are commonly found in uncontrolled regions or places where there are environmental issues like pollution.

Poor housing, unpleasant living conditions, overcrowding, instability, and unskilled laborers laboring in low-paying jobs like construction and small trading are all characteristics of Nairobi's slums. Slums are defined by the Kenyan government's new land policy as unplanned, insecurely

occupied informal communities. But in Nairobi, the majority of slums grow on privately owned land intended for public usage. People who live in slums built their homes in unapproved locations.

The local initiative, which had the support of both the national and municipal governments, was the project's success story. Gykomba slum residents created a cooperative organization for housing renovation as part of the initiative (UN-Habitat, 2008). Slum residents assisted in the building of the new town with work and monetary donations. The National Corporation, a subsidiary of the government, also provided secured loans for the project's finance. The slum residents considered the project their initiative because of their active engagement, which was one lesson gained from the project.

2.10.2 Case Study Area Two: Funding Durban Slum Housing (South Africa)

The second-most significant manufacturing center in South Africa after Johannesburg is Durban, the country's largest city. The expansion of the sugar and food processing industries is correlated with the rise of Durban. South Africa's eastern coast is home to Durban, whose municipality spans 2,300 kilometers. On either private or public grounds, the informal settlements have grown inside the city limits. Private landowners have permitted informal settlement on their property in exchange for rent.

In South Africa, there are various ways to define slums. For instance, the provincial Department of Housing describes slums as "loosely used to refer to informal settlements" and as "erstwhile formal communities that have degenerated to such an extent that there exists a need to restore them to acceptable standards" (Department of Housing, KwaZulu-Natal, 2002 as cited by Marx C. and Charlton S. 2003)

Structures built with a variety of materials, such as corrugated iron, plastic, timber, and metal sheeting, and with varying degrees of permanency are what define the informal settlements of Durban. There are instances where wattle and daub building are employed. Typically, linoleum or carpeting is placed over the earth, which is the floor. Water is supplied through communal taps and sometimes by natural sources like rivers, and sanitation is provided by a makeshift pit latrine.

A "Slum Clearance Programme" was developed by the Provincial Housing Department, which provides funding for the growth of unofficial settlements. Additionally, "top-up" funds were given to the housing project as an addition to the national subsidy allotment. A multi-year initiative to

enhance conditions in informal settlements using the Metro Housing Development Account to improve additional funds when appropriate is one of the significant policy pledges made by the Thekwini Council.

It has been discovered how important it is to involve slum residents in slum housing repair projects because it will be exceedingly challenging to carry out a project in an informal settlement without their cooperation.

2.11 Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework aids in problem-solving by illustrating the cause-and-effect relationships that surround a given issue. It entails prioritizing problems and decomposing problems into more manageable sizes to diagnose problems. It presents a problem graphically, with the main branches representing the primary causes that led to the problem. This activity helps to further examine causes until a series of causes leading to root causes are found by stimulating and broadening thinking about potential or actual causes (Weiss et al, 2000). The conceptual framework was created to identify the causes of the focal problem, the root causes, and the consequences of the problem after the characteristics and problems of slum housing development were identified and prioritized from the questionnaire survey. Based on the results of this analysis, a conceptual framework (see figure 2.1) was created, outlining the underlying causes, the main issue, and the effects. Government intervention in the construction of slum housing was made possible by this, serving as both a basis and a starting point.

Figure 2.1: Conceptual framework

2.12 Conclusion

This chapter argued that slum dwellers who fall under the low-income bracket construct their own homes using a self-help gradual method. This process reflects the housing needs of low-income households and, in particular, their precarious financial situation. Therefore, the duration of the continuous building process is determined by the low-income group's income levels, and it occasionally lasts for generations through several phases. It made the case that affordability, appropriateness, and adaptability are the three major characteristics of incremental housing. By spreading out the effects of construction costs and income availability, affordability is achieved.

Furthermore, it has been proposed that by a coordinated policy that focuses on targeted subsidies and household savings, the government can assist low-income groups in achieving home ownership through the incremental housing process. To demonstrate this idea, Kenya and South Africa were used as case studies.

CHAPTER THREE

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Introduction

This research chapter describes the research methodology. Sampling methods, data sources, and various data collection tools and techniques are discussed. This chapter also describes techniques used in data processing, analysis, and reporting.

3.2 Research Design

The research describes the entire strategy chosen to bring together disparate study components understandably and analytically, safeguarding the study's ability to effectively address the research's problem. It primarily includes the plan for data collection, data measurement, and data analysis. According to Trochim (2006), the type of design you can choose depends on the study problem.

The goal of a research design is to make sure that the data you gather will help you accurately address the questions raised by the study. Casual, descriptive, and exploratory study designs are the three primary forms of research design. When used properly, these three designs will help the researcher organize the study efficiently. Each of the three designs offers instructions for resolving various challenges. According to Trochim (2006), the research problem reveals the best form of research design to use, hence a sample survey was used for this study.

Surveys are a widely used type of research design. It entails interviewing and surveying participants to get information. To increase the representativeness of a larger population, data are collected here using standardized forms and from carefully selected samples. An effective way to visualize a group's current situation is through a survey. As stated by Bryman (2004), Fellows and Liu (2008), and Janes (1999), the survey incorporates more participants than an experimental design and can include correlations between variables' perceptions and behaviors.

The study looked at slum inhabitants' housing characteristics and living situations. Its primary goal was to explore and analyze novel means of financing slum improvement in Aboabo, as well as to make recommendations for improving slum housing. The case study approach was used in the study's cross-sectional research design. This resulted in the production of grounded results from an in-depth investigation into a slum to meet the study's aims.

According to the problem statement, the case study area is the Aboabo Township in Kumasi, the capital of Ghana's Ashanti Region. The case study area was selected despite its deplorable environmental conditions and lack of development. The neighborhood is considered to be underdeveloped due to congestion, subpar housing options, and poor development siting, all of which contribute to unhealthy environmental conditions. A visit to the township demonstrates its extreme environmental conditions, making it eligible to be labeled a slum. Chapter Three of this paper provides a thorough description of these traits.

3.3 Sample Techniques

The study used both probability and non-probability sampling methods. To choose the institutions and research region, non-probability sampling was applied. However, snowball sampling was used to choose respondents since the researcher wanted to discover landlords who were available during the field investigation.

3.3.1 Sample frame

Houses in Aboabo served as the study's sample frame, from which the sample size was calculated. As of 2010, it had 830 dwellings (KMA, 2010).

3.3.2 Sampling Size Determination

This seeks to select a subset of the population to reflect the total population. As a result, information will be gathered from a subset of the population to make conclusions for the full research area.

The sample size for the investigation was determined using the formula below:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(\alpha)^2}$$

Where n is the sample size, big N is the sample frame and α is the level of significance or margin of error. The sample size was determined at a 90% confidence level to ensure a fair representative sample size (at a 0.1 significance level).

$$n = \frac{830}{1 + 830(0.1)^2}$$

$$n = 89.25$$

The sample size is approximately 90 households

Based on the computation, 90 questionnaires were administered in Aboabo.

3.4 Profile of Study Area

3.4.1 Kumasi

The importance of Kumasi in the Ghanaian economy can be linked to its function in the country's service and industrial sectors, where it serves as a hub for many commercial and public service providers as well as heavy and light industries. Kumasi's favorable geographic and economic location has aided in the city's rapid expansion and development. Due to its central location in the large-scale, lucrative distribution of goods and services both domestically and internationally, the primary transport terminal has been given this responsibility. Due to Kumasi's significance to regional and national growth, the resulting urbanization and economic activity have resulted in activities that have caused a rapid population expansion due to migration, resulting in the creation of slum communities.

By the Local Government Act 462, 1993, and Local Government Legislative Instrument L.I. 1614, 1989, the Kumasi Metropolitan Assembly (KMA), which oversees the city, was established. These legal frameworks have also granted the KMA the ability to pass rules and bylaws that give the organization's choices legitimacy. The Local Government Act 462 (1993) and Legislative Instrument (L.I.) 1614 also provide KMA the jurisdiction to become a planning authority, with the ability to create policies, plans, and programs as well as to mobilize resources within its scope to carry out development initiatives. Nine sub-metros currently make up Kumasi: Bantama, Subin, Manhyia, Oforikrom, Tafo, Nhyiaeso, Kwadaso, Suame, and Asokwa. Up until 2012, the Asawase sub-metro was the tenth in the Kumasi Metropolitan Assembly. Currently, it is a constituent of the recently established Asokore-Mampong Municipal Assembly, which includes Aboabo. A legislative instrument, L.I. 2112, was used to establish the Municipal Assembly.

3.4.2 Aboabo

A reconnaissance survey conducted by UN-Habitat in the Kumasi Metropolis to create slum profiles led to the identification of several neighborhoods, including Aboabo (KMA, 2005). It's situated off the Kumasi-Accra trunk road on the eastern by-pass, about 4.5 kilometers (km) east of the CBD. A total of 1.6 km² of land is occupied by Aboabo, which is a part of the recently

established Asokore Mampong Municipal Assembly. This Kumasi community is a Zongo community. "A camping location for caravans" or "a lodging place for travelers" is what the Hausa word "Zongo" means (Abraham as cited in Sarfo, 1986). Aboabo has several issues: bad sanitation, big households, shoddy construction, traffic, and inadequate utility service delivery. It is a slum due to all of these features.

The reason Aboabo was chosen for the study is that it is a slum neighborhood with all the issues and challenges that slum people deal with. Poor living conditions characterize the low-income neighborhood of Aboabo. About 10,000 residents of Aboabo live in substandard housing, which is the majority of the population (Kumasi Metropolitan Assembly [KMA], 2006).

Figure 3.1: Map Showing the Geographical Location of Aboabo Settlement

Source: Author's Construct (2022)

3.4.2.1 Historical Evolution

The name "aboo," which in the Akan dialect means "rocky ground," refers to the area's rocky and undulating topography. Due to its rough terrain, the locals once thought that this location was unsuitable for habitation. Due to the influx of migrants looking for work from the Northern regions of the former Gold Coast (Ghana), among other migrants, Aboabo has been created. As they made an effort to support themselves, the migrants built transitory constructions nearby. The migrants

asked their friends and family to join them when they learned how serene the region was and how simple it was to acquire drinking water because River Aboabo was nearby. As permanent structures were built to house a vast number of individuals who had flocked there, the area started to take shape. (Community Leader, individual communication, June 2022).

3.4.2.2 Population

The 2010 Population and Housing Census Report estimates that 44,577 people are living in Aboabo. The survey also notes that the neighborhood's growth rate is 2.68%. (Ghana Statistical Service, 2010). Compared to Kumasi, which has a population growth rate of 5.4. Aboabo's rate of population increase is considerably lower. According to the population and housing census conducted in 2010, Aboabo's growth rate is nearly equal to Ghana's 2.7% national growth rate.

Table 3.1: Aboabo's Population and Growth Rate

YEAR	POPULATION	POPULATION GROWTH RATE
1970	16,724	
1984	22,636	2.19
2000	34,206	2.61
2010	44,577	2.68

Source: Ghana Statistical Service (2014)

3.4.2.3 Infrastructure and Housing.

Because there isn't enough room to build these amenities, Quaye-Ballard et al. (2009) noted in their research report that Aboabo has relatively few infrastructure facilities such as motorable roads, proper sewers, bathroom facilities, trash dumps, and access to pipe-borne water.

A nucleated habitation pattern is present at Aboabo. This is a pattern of settlement that develops around a hub. Most of the time, there is little to no space between the residences that are joined to one another. Additionally, a visual inspection would reveal that the majority of the houses have additions (extra constructions) that were not originally intended.

Plate 3.1: Image showing a wooden kitchen extension attached to the main building

Source: Field Survey (2022)

Few buildings in the neighborhood have a kitchen integrated into the main structure or a bathroom and toilet built into the building as part of the original design due to the older age and style of the majority of the structures. Upon closer observation, one might see some business structures, especially near the main roadways. The contemporary quality of these buildings' architectural designs distinguished them. These commercial structures were typically multi-story structures with tiled floors, glazed windows, and colored corrugated roofing sheets on many of them. Offices and retail stores were housed in commercial structures.

Only a small number of the residential structures in the Aboabo settlement have been renovated using cement blocks; the majority were constructed of mud. The majority of the mud-built structures are rendered with cement and painted. However, there are lots of wooden buildings. The principal houses' kitchens are frequently housed in these wooden buildings. Most homes have aluminum roofs, while there are a few instances of story buildings with parapet roofs. But the majority of the roofing elements are rusted, which strongly suggests that they haven't been replaced in a very long period. Most roofs had pieces of sandcrete blocks placed on them to assist hold down the roofing materials due to the strong winds that sometimes accompanied heavy rainfall. Cement

screed is used to finish the inner court in the majority of compound homes. There are a lot of compound houses in the neighborhood.

In most cases, there are no drains in front of the houses, and some sections of the community's road system are simply impassable to motor vehicles. The foundation of some structures may crumble and become exposed as a result of inadequate drainage, which may result in flooding.

3.4.2.4 Sanitation and Drainage.

Due to Aboabo's weak drainage system, the area is vulnerable to flooding. According to the KMA (2006), the community's haphazard construction, particularly along the River Aboabo waterway, adds to the occurrence of persistent floods in the area. Along the main thoroughfares that go through the neighborhood, substantial drains are built. In the Aboabo township, there are numerous places where stagnant water is trapped in wide open spaces as a result of the overall lack of properly built drains. Where there are drains, the majority of them are congested and unable to transport run-off water from heavy rains.

There aren't many residences that have areas for convenience in terms of sanitation. Therefore, the majority of the population uses the community's public restrooms. However, some of the residents engage in "free range" behavior, which involves urinating in public areas, particularly gutters. Residents of the neighborhood may dispose of their rubbish at shared dump sites. The amount of trash is what determines the charge for disposal in this case. Garbage being put into drains and left to lay around is a typical occurrence, though. The ongoing, careless dumping of both solid and liquid garbage in the neighborhood has significantly increased the contamination of River Aboabo. The majority of gutters empty their contents into the River Aboabo, rendering the water unsafe for drinking.

3.4.2.5 Services

The Aboabo settlement is supplied with water by the Ghana Water Company Limited (GWCL). There aren't many homes that directly receive GWCL water because of pipe restrictions. The fact that most homes lack direct access to pipe-borne water from the GWCL can be partially explained by the expense as well as the unpredictable nature of the GWCL's water supply. Some homes additionally have mechanized wells, boreholes, and water reservoirs, while others use GWCL's public standpipes to get both private water sellers' water and potable water.

The Kumasi Metropolis and Aboabo are well connected by well-paved highways. Roads connecting Aboabo to Oforikrom, the Kumasi Airport, Asawase, and Asokore-Mampong are a few examples of tarmac roads in the neighborhood. However, there isn't anything to complain about with the neighborhood's internal roadways. Some of the routes are just impassable to motor vehicles because of their narrowness and the terrain. Accessibility to homes in some areas of the township is quite challenging due to unpaved roads connecting numerous residences and the chaotic arrangement of homes in the neighborhood.

There are numerous Islamic schools (makarantah) scattered throughout the largely Muslim population of Aboabo. In the neighborhood, there are a variety of secular private and public schools. Along the community's main highways, there are a lot of retail stores, kiosks, and "tabletop sellers" that sell groceries and other consumables. The township also has a market that caters to the locals.

3.4.2.6 Economic and Social Characteristics

Three regions of northern Ghana - Upper East, Upper West, and Northern - are home to most of the community's population. The community does have a minority of other ethnic groups, though. The most common language in Aboabo is Hausa, even though Twi is the most common language in the Ashanti Region and Kumasi.

In Aboabo, there are 21,843 males and 22,734 females, according to the 2010 population and housing census. The big population in the community may be linked to the area's predominance of the Islamic religion, which promotes polygamy and creates large families. However, there is evidence of Christianity in the area because it is home to several churches.

In the neighborhood, there is a strong sense of community. This could be explained by the predominant religion in the region (Islam). Islam emphasizes communal life. This may be demonstrated by the clustered structure of the majority of old homes. One might run into various families in the community who have a common grandfather in some locations. Another typical scene is a group of young people engaging in intensive conversation, playing football, or drinking draught. The majority of the homes in the neighborhood were passed down through families.

One of the low-income areas in the Kumasi Metropolis is designated as the location in question. Some characteristics of low-income communities are readily apparent in the layout of the

community's buildings, the general state of the area's cleanliness, the shoddy construction of the community's roadways, and the presence of convenience stores (public toilets). Because there isn't a solid and regular maintenance culture, the majority of the buildings in the region are in horrible shape. The community's low level of income and education is to blame for the absence of a maintenance culture there.

Most Aboabo residents work for themselves in the unorganized sector due to the low level of education in the area (Ghana Statistical Service, 2010, Melese, 2006). However, most members of the community work in either the public or private sectors. While the majority of men work in basic vocations like carpentry, masonry, plumbing, and shoemaking to mention a few, the majority of women are involved in small-scale trading.

3.5 Data Collection Method

As stated by Nenty (2009), to address the research topic, it is necessary to technically separate the relationship existing among and between variables in an instance and then examine the association without inessential influences. As a result, Nenty (2009) emphasized once more that study design contains processes used to discover and analyze the link that exists among variables in our situations, as well as to debate the choice of some procedures over others. As a result, the research design becomes the master plan that directs how the research will be carried out. The primary and secondary materials were used in synchrony for the investigation. The employment of both provides credibility to the research (Patton, 1990).

To achieve the study's objectives, both quantitative and qualitative data collection approaches were used. This study's data was gathered using a variety of tools. Data were obtained using both primary and secondary sources.

3.5.1 Primary Data Sources

The research field is the main source of data. A variety of tools were used to accomplish this. These are some examples:

- Interviews
- Direct observation
- Photography

3.5.1.1 Interviews

The sample units (landlords) in the various neighborhoods were personally interviewed using questionnaires. The questionnaires were mostly pre-coded with a few open-ended questions thrown in for good measure.

3.5.1.2 Direct observation

To acquire qualitative data, the study employs observation techniques. The goal of employing this technique was to be able to photograph the housing conditions in the chosen areas. This allowed information to be deduced with information from other sources. The non-participant observation technique was used in conjunction with the provision of questionnaires and interviews. Because it is necessary to obtain the permission of property owners before taking images, participants were told about the purpose of the study to obtain their agreement. In addition, direct observation was employed due to the requirement to be as oblivious as possible to avoid bias in the observation process. The researcher personally examined the physical characteristics of the houses while taking pictures of residences. Visual objects were created from the attributes' physical characteristics.

3.5.2 Secondary Data Sources

An extensive desktop review of the body of existing research on the subject was required for the secondary data sources. Public and private books, research papers, periodicals, newspapers, and statutes were all included in the works consulted. For the thesis's research and writing, the Internet has also been a really useful resource.

3.6 Data Analysis

A spreadsheet and the Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) version 26.00 are used to code and analyze the questionnaires that were sent out to respondents. The results from the surveys and interviews were interpreted using the techniques listed above. To supplement the discussion in this study, the data obtained is presented in both tabular and graphical formats. Respondents' background information is displayed via bar graphs and pie charts. The findings of this study are compared to the research objectives and questions. The analysis of the qualitative data obtained from observation involved summarizing, characterizing, and reconciling it with other qualitative and quantitative data. Pictures were used to illustrate some of the observational data that was gathered.

3.7 Chapter Summary

The many methodologies used in this study were discussed in this chapter, along with the justifications for doing so. Both the research approach used and the data collection technique were discussed. The chapter's conclusion covered the study procedure as well as topics like the population, data sources, questionnaire design, questionnaire content and design, sample size determination, data presentation, and analysis.

CHAPTER FOUR

DATA ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Fieldwork

The research began with a reconnaissance survey of Aboabo, the subject location, to assess the social, physical, and housing conditions there. To get information from the residents of Aboabo, questionnaires were later developed. In addition, three pertinent institutions and three local leaders' interview materials were developed. The community's leaders, in particular the chiefs and assemblymen for both Aboabo No. 1 and Aboabo No. 2, were called and briefed about the study and its goals. The researcher then went ahead and administered the surveys in the study area after getting the go-ahead from the local officials. The right officials were scheduled and interviewed for the institutions that were pertinent to the study. Questionnaires, pencils, introductory letters, and student ID cards were among the materials used to administer the survey. Various areas that were thought to be pertinent to the study were also photographed.

4.2 Respondents' Age Distribution

When dealing with residents of informal settlements, their message is a crucial factor that must be taken into account. The respondents' ages vary from 32 to 72, with a typical age of 45. To evaluate the group that was evaluated the most frequently, the respondents' ages were divided into 5-year intervals.

Table 4.1: Respondents' Age Distribution

AGE	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE (%)
32-36	2	8
37-41	4	21
42-46	18	7
47-51	32	9
52-56	13	18

57-61	1	24
62-66	7	8
67-71	8	4
72-76	5	1
TOTAL	90	100

Source: Field Survey (2022)

Thirty-seven (37) years old respondents made up twenty-one (21) percent of all respondents, followed by respondents aged 57–61 (24%). The respondents' age distribution revealed that the majority of the landlords were elderly, with sixty-four (64) percent of the respondents between the ages of 47 and 76.

In addition, 85 men and 15 women were among the responses, or 85% and 15%, respectively. This demonstrates the cultural component of home ownership, particularly in patrilineal societies where culture expects the man to be the breadwinner and own a home. Men always want to be recognized and respected in every society, and as a result, they frequently believe that owning a home will result in some level of social restructuring. Property ownership raises one's social status in society.

Figure 4.1: Respondents' Gender Composition

Source: Field Survey (2022)

The Respondent's Length Of Stay

The data collected in Aboabo shows that the majority of the slum dwellers have been a part of the neighborhood for a considerable amount of time. The remaining 4% of respondents have resided for less than 15 years, compared to the 96% of respondents who have lived for more than 16 years. The slum dwellers' extended presence suggests that they are more settled in the region and are therefore more familiar with the overall way of life of Aboabo's residents.

Table 4.2: Length of Respondent's Stay In Aboabo

PERIOD OF YEARS	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE (%)
0-5	4	1
6-10	2	3
11-15	0	0.0

16-20	11	10
21-25	15	13
26-30	3	11
31-35	9	13
36-40	20	20
Above 41	26	29
TOTAL	90	100

Source: Field Survey (2022)

4.3 The Respondents' Level of Education

High levels of illiteracy and low educational attainment among residents are frequent characteristics of informal settlements (slums) (Nawagamuwa and Viking, 2003). Out of the 90 respondents, 50% had never had any kind of formal education; 20 had completed their primary education, albeit it was clear from the interview that the majority of these respondents had not finished their primary education. In this case, it was also discovered that some respondents had not been able to complete their education at that level, with financial constraints being the main obstacle for the majority of them. Thirteen (13) respondents had also completed their education up to the secondary/vocational/technical level. It was discovered that the majority of respondents with education up to the secondary, vocational, or technical levels were working in the formal economy as teachers. Only one (2) respondent had a degree from a university (technical university). It was discovered that the majority of respondents who had only completed middle school or junior high school were largely independent contractors working in the unorganized sector in jobs like petty trading, carpentry, and sewing. Given the low wages associated with these professions, it may be easier to understand why the majority of homeowners found it challenging to make improvements to their homes. It should be emphasized that the group of people described in the previous statement accounts for at least 86 percent of all responses. Most of the respondents with education up to the secondary, vocational, technical, and university levels worked as teachers. Such individuals should earn more than the other category, all other things being equal. Fourteen (14)

percent of all respondents were respondents who had completed secondary, vocational, technical, or tertiary education, and these respondents had monthly incomes above GH¢ 300, which is typically not the case for respondents who completed their education below secondary, vocational, technical, or tertiary education.

Figure 4.2: The Respondents' Level of Education

Source: Field Survey (2022)

4.4 Expenditure

With 67% of respondents saying they spend most of their income on food for their households, it is clear that food is the largest expense in respondents' households. As the second-highest household expense, food was listed by 33 (33% of the respondents) as being purchased. Sixty-eight (68) percent of respondents said they spent the least money on water and electricity, while only two said they spent the most. Thirty (30) percent of respondents ranked it as their second biggest expense, while two said it was their highest. Thirty-one percent of the respondents said they considered health and education to be their highest spending, 37% said it was their second highest expenditure, and 31% said it is their lowest cost. From the data, it can be deduced that

respondents prioritize spending on food, with 67% of respondents saying that this is their biggest outlay. Water and electricity are seen as their two lowest expenses by sixty-eight (68%) percent of the respondents.

Figure 4.3: Housing expenditure of respondents

Source: Field Survey (2022)

4.5 The Respondents' Income

It was also noticed that the majority of the respondents had additional sources of income, including rent revenues, petty trading, and remittances from their children, in addition to their main employment or occupations, which were their primary sources of income.

Out of the 90 respondents, 45, or 45%, reported having a monthly income of more than GH¢ 300, while 34%, or 34 respondents, reported having a monthly income of between GH¢ 251 and GH¢ 300. In addition, 11 of our respondents make between GH¢ 201 and GH¢ 250, while the remaining 10 respondents, or 10% of the sample, make between GH¢ 150 and GH¢ 200. The slum inhabitants' poor income relative to their expenses suggests that they are unable to invest much in improving their living conditions. Additionally, the economic activities that slum inhabitants take part in can be linked to the trend in income.

Furthermore, the study showed that the majority of respondents fall into the GH¢ 251–300 and GH¢ 150–200 income brackets. Traders, and civil and public servants made up the majority of the homeowners who fit into these categories. The majority of the workforce, excluding civil and public servants, worked in the informal economy. These are the income brackets that are ineligible for housing financing, so people in these groups would have to fulfill their innate desire to own a home on their relatively modest incomes. It also supports the claim made by Ferguson (2003) and Greene and Rojas (2008) that the majority of slum dwellers have low incomes, which may fluctuate depending on the individual's employment situation. The table depicts the respondent's income levels.

Table 4.3: The Respondents' Income

INCOME	PERCENTAGE (%)
GH¢ 150 – 200	10
GH¢ 201 – 250	11
GH¢ 251 – 300	34
More than GH¢ 301	45

Source: Field Survey (2022)

4.6 Housing Conditions for Slum Inhabitants In Aboabo

In this part, the housing circumstances of Aboabo's slum residents are examined. The following categories are taken into consideration: land tenure, community roadways, building supplies, and access to basic amenities including water, power, and waste disposal.

4.6.1 Land tenure

The slum residents of Aboabo possess the land through the chiefs. Twenty-eight (28) percent of the respondents, claimed to have purchased the land. The researcher identified these as leasehold interests. Additionally, 66 respondents, or 66 percent of the sample size said they received the land from their family, whereas 6 respondents, or 6 percent of the sample said they were on community land. Since the majority of respondents (94%) obtained their properties through official channels, assuring them of their titles, it makes them more willing to improve their lands because they have the security of tenure.

Figure 4.4: Land Acquisition/Ownership

Source: Field Survey (2022)

The study found that the primary method by which slum house owners obtain land is through purchases from traditional landowners. In most cases, developers buy a piece of land long before it needs to be developed. The acquisition of land, whether legally or illegally, is the first step in incremental housing development, as stated by Ferguson (2003) and Greene and Rojas (2008). However, the land is legally acquired in the study area according to established customs. This is due to the nature of Ghana's customary land tenure system, where each traditional authority is very watchful of its territory to guard against unauthorized entry.

4.6.2 Slum House Building Materials

The survey revealed that the houses in the slum area were mostly made of landcrete and sandcrete blocks, zinc, wood, bamboo, and mud. According to the results of the field survey, 67 respondents built their homes out of landcrete and bamboo. The buildings, however, were finished with cement mortar. Since the buildings have become termite infested, this technique has taken a toll on their maintenance. Furthermore, crack and render fall-offs expose the buildings to adverse weather. Again, 31 respondents used sandcrete blocks in the construction of their buildings, with only two

respondents primarily using wood. These were simple wooden planks with no blockwork. The settlement's housing maintenance is poor, and the building materials are not long-lasting.

Plate 4.1: Image showing non-durable materials used in construction

Source: Field Survey (2022)

Plate 4.2: Image showing falling roof

Source: Field Survey (2022)

Forty-eight percent (48%) of the 61% had leaking roofs, while the remaining 12% had blocks on their roofs because they claimed the roofs flew off during the rainy season when there were storms. Most landcrete builders had walls, few complained of roof leaks, and quite a few (20 out of 67) had blocks on their roofs to keep them from flying away when it rained.

Figure 4.5: Building Materials of Houses In Aboabo

Source: Field Survey (2022)

4.6.3 Aboabo Housing Conditions

Aboabo has a poor housing maintenance culture, and the building materials used in house construction are not long-lasting. As a result, the majority of the houses in the area have housing issues. According to the findings of the field survey, 72 percent of respondents reported having problems with their home's roofing and want to improve it. Furthermore, 58 percent thought it was necessary to improve their exterior walls. They desired to make improvements such as rendering their walls, painting their structures, and patching cracks. Furthermore, 22% thought it was necessary to improve the foundation of their homes. The foundations of those houses have been subjected to adverse weather conditions, particularly erosion, which is eroding them.

Plate 4.3: Image showing exposed foundation

Source: Field Survey (2022)

Furthermore, 57 percent of respondents saw the need to improve their floors. The majority of the floors were made of cement screed, but they were cracked. The researchers also discovered that 30% of respondents desired to improve their homes. Furthermore, the majority of respondents desired to make additions and improvements such as adding toilets, bathrooms, kitchens, and building gates. This reveals slum dwellers' expectations for better sanitation and social status through the appearance of their homes. The graph depicts the areas of the house that respondents would like to improve.

Figure 4.6: House Improvements Needed in Certain Areas

Source: Field Survey (2022)

An evaluation of the respondents' housing in Aboabo is shown in the graph below. The roof, floor, foundation, and exterior walls of each house are taken into consideration. Worse, Bad, Regular, Good, and Very Good were the different categories assigned to the conditions. Houses in worse conditions had unpainted walls with significant cracks, roof leaks, floors with holes and cracks, and sinking foundations. Although not to the extent of worse conditions, bad conditions meant that the homes had cracked walls, leaking roofs, holes in the floor and cracks, and sinking foundations. The houses were in average condition, which meant that they weren't in particularly good or bad shape. Homes in good condition have clean, painted walls with hairline cracks, slightly leaking roofs, a strong foundation, and no floor cracks. Very good conditions meant no cracks or holes in the painted walls, no roof leaks, no floor cracks or holes, and a strong foundation.

Figure 4.7 Aboabo's Housing Condition

Source: Field Survey (2022)

Twenty-eight (28) percent of respondents thought their home's roofing was in worse shape, which is a sizable percentage. Additionally, their exterior wall, foundation, and floor were all rated as being in worse condition by 11 percent, 8 percent, and 17 percent, respectively. Additionally, a remarkable 47% of respondents also thought poorly of the state of their exterior walls and roof, respectively. Additionally, 21% and 36% of respondents thought their floor and foundation were both bad. According to 24% of respondents, their roofing is in good condition, followed by 28% who said the same about their exterior walls, and then 48% and 31% said the same about their foundation and floor. Unbelievably, 20 percent of homeowners think their roofing is in good shape, and 14 percent think their exterior walls are in good shape. The soundness of their floors and foundations is also attested to by 23 and 16 percent of respondents, respectively. None of the respondents thought their homes were in very good shape.

4.6.4 Aboabo's availability and accessibility to basic services

The presence of facilities and services is intended to make life easier for residents. Housing encompasses not only the physical structure but also all other basic services. Access to basic

services such as water, electricity, and garbage disposal is required for a building to be considered standard. These services exist, but they are insufficient.

In terms of home water access, 48 percent have pipe connections from public mains, 40 percent have no access to water in their homes and must rely on water vendors, 9 percent have access to wells, and only 3 percent have access to mechanized boreholes.

Figure 4.8: Water Accessibility

Source: Field Survey (2022)

Despite the presence of pipe connections in some homes, water rarely flows. Some respondents complained that this is due to exposed pipelines that are broken and have not been repaired. Aboabo's taps open at 8 a.m. and close around 9 p.m. This affects households that lack adequate water storage facilities.

In terms of waste disposal, 64 percent have access to the communal dumpsite, and 18 percent give theirs to garbage collectors for a fee based on the volume of waste. Sixteen percent (16%) burn theirs; one percent (1%) bury theirs in holes, and one percent (1%) leave them in the open. Observations made during the fieldwork revealed that some residents dispose of their trash in gutters. This can be attributed to the dumpsite's distance from the community.

Figure 4.9: Aboabo Waste Disposal

Source: Field Survey (2022)

In terms of roads, 95 percent of respondents said their streets needed to be improved. Only 5% of slum dwellers disagreed with the need to improve the streets. These people live along the main streets and did not think it was necessary to improve the streets. However, it was found that 96 percent of the population was impacted by road dust. Those with access to cars were also inconvenienced by the potholes.

Figure 4.10: Respondents who wanted improvement to the streets

Source: Field Survey (2022)

4.6.5 Access Roads

It was noted that the majority of the access roads in the study area were not paved. The properties further from the main streets were found to have less clearly defined streets.

4.6.6 Access to Electricity

According to the survey, 96% of the area was connected to public mains. Even though the neighborhood had an electricity connection, the remaining 4% were not connected to the power grid.

4.7 Financing Options for Building

Slum dwellers face significant difficulties in financing construction. Because of their low incomes, these people frequently have only a few options for financing the construction of their homes. This mainly results in them using their hard-earned savings to build their typically unsatisfactory homes. As evidenced by the fieldwork at Aboabo, some property owners use rent earnings from other buildings they own. The survey revealed various sources of financing for buildings in Aboabo. The options vary from loans, personal savings, and rent proceeds. Those who took out

bank loans were salaried workers who applied for personal consumption loans to speed up the construction of their homes.

According to the data gathered, 62 percent of slum dwellers financed their buildings with personal savings. In addition, 22 percent used their rent proceeds, 4 percent borrowed, and 12 percent had no idea how the building was funded. (Figure 4.12)

Figure 4.11: Financing Options for Building

Source: Field Work (2022)

The slum dwellers who had no idea about the building's financing attributed this to the fact that they are only caretakers or owners by inheritance. Eighty percent (80%) of slum dwellers got their houses through inheritance, one percent worked as a caretaker, seventeen percent built them, and two percent bought them. (See Figure 4.13)

Figure 4.12: Means of Obtaining House

Source: Field Survey (2022)

The low percentage of loans used to finance home construction demonstrates the loan system's low patronage. Some respondents expressed dissatisfaction with the formal bank loan system. The interest to be paid and other factors considered during the underwriting process do not qualify them for bank loans. Their income level also explains why they were unable to obtain loans to construct their homes.

4.7.1 Finance for Housing Improvement

Only 13 of the 90 respondents had recently made any type of improvement to the current state of their home in terms of financing housing improvements. Eight respondents (62 percent) of the 13 respondents (representing 100 percent) used their rent proceeds to make improvements to their homes, while five respondents (38 percent) used their savings. It was discovered during the interview that the respondents who had recently made improvements had done so because new tenants were moving in or when there were family gatherings. These additions included enlarging verandas, building a bathroom, re-roofing specific areas of the house, and painting and plastering.

More than half of the 90 respondents (77 percent) had not made any improvements to their homes in the previous three years. The majority of those polled cited a lack of funds as the reason they had not made any improvements to their homes. Some respondents also stated that they made improvements to their building when an incoming tenant requested it, whereas others stated that there had been no family function (funerals, weddings, and naming ceremonies), so they had not made any improvements.

Figure 4.13: Housing Financing Suggestions

Source: Field Survey (2022)

Forty-eight percent of the 90 respondents said that if they had the option to finance, they would do so from their savings. Respondents who suggested personal savings as an option cited religious reasons, economic convenience, and their social status as reasons for their preference. Aboabo is a predominantly Muslim community, and the Islamic religion forbids them from charging interest on loans and, by extension, paying interest on loans.

According to the respondents' responses to interviews, loans, in general, are not preferred, especially loans from banks. Because of the interest, they would have to pay, some respondents claimed they did not want bank loans. Others avoided loans altogether due to their religious beliefs. Due to their low income and level of education, the majority of the respondents had little interest

in banks or other formal banking institutions. Only three of the 90 respondents suggested bank loans as a solution. Whereas 22 respondents indicated that cooperative society loans were their preferred housing financing option. The fact that only three percent of respondents preferred bank loans reflects their general dislike of bank loans.

According to the available data, 41 percent of respondents had rent proceeds as an additional source of income, while 21 percent stated rent proceeds as their primary source of income. Most of the respondents were owners of their homes through inheritance, purchase, or construction, with only one being a caretaker, implying that the majority of them have access to rental income. Twenty-seven percent of respondents said they would prefer rent proceeds as a financing option. The majority of such respondents stated that they preferred rent proceeds as a financing option because it is a consistent source of income for the majority of them and can be accumulated over time and used to improve housing conditions. Others stated that it was money they did not need to borrow in comparison to loans from banks and other financial institutions. Rent proceeds can be saved or invested in other income-generating businesses to be used to improve housing.

From the analysis, it can be concluded that equity financing—in the form of individual savings and rent proceeds—is generally preferred over debt financing—in the form of bank loans and loans from cooperative societies. According to the information at hand, 75% of respondents favor equity financing (personal savings and rent proceeds), while only 25% would prefer debt financing (loans from banks and cooperative societies). Among the 25% of respondents who prefer debt financing, 12% prefer loans from banks, while 78% prefer loans from cooperative societies. This demonstrates how respondents are generally loan-averse, particularly bank loan-averse.

Figure 4.14: Suggestions for Housing Finance in Aboabo

Source: Field Survey (2022)

4.8 Institutional Initiatives for Kumasi's Housing Improvement

This section looks into how government agencies may help slum communities in Kumasi with housing issues. To understand more about the activities that take place in slum communities, representatives from the Physical Planning Department (PPD), the Electricity Company of Ghana (ECG), the Ghana Water Company Limited (GWCL), and the Asokore-Mampong Municipal Assembly (AMMA) were interviewed.

4.8.1 Planning (Physical Planning Department)

Slums emerged in Kumasi as a result of rapid urbanization, according to the PPD. According to them, the migrants initially settled in kiosks and other temporary structures in communities such as Asawase-Zongo, Aboabo, and Ayigyia-Zongo, to name a few. Such areas are in disrepair and are characterized by low-income families who cannot afford decent city housing.

They added that an area like Aboabo was intended to be a residential neighborhood with basic amenities like schools, sanitary facilities, and open spaces, but due to the city's rapid population growth and the insatiable demand for housing, it has turned into a slum. The respondent added that

the absence of base maps is their biggest problem with zoning, development control, and planning. He claimed that the cost of updating the old maps was extremely expensive, and there were no resources available. This challenge forces PPD to build the city without adequate maps or spatial data. Zoning plan enforcement was also a problem because community chiefs sometimes sold community space to people for private use.

4.8.2 Provision of Utility Services: Ghana Water Company Limited, Electricity Company of Ghana, and Waste Management Department.

According to the Ghana Water Company Limited (GWCL), the service's affordability is a challenge because most slum dwellers cannot afford it. They also stated that in some cases, there is either a lack of service or a higher cost of accessing the service in slums. Ghana Water Company Limited also stated that unplanned areas are typically excluded from the city's pipeline distribution network because they lack detailed layout plans.

The ECG stated that slums were temporary settlements. They stated that they could provide power on major roads in Aboabo, but that they needed permission from the government to extend electricity services to the entire community. They also stated that they could not provide electricity to the entire slum community because some residents could not afford it. The majority of people have been able to receive electricity, according to the ECG. Even though the power supply was insufficient for all of the households. Additionally, they claimed that the community's detailed plans, which were necessary for electricity provision, were unavailable.

The residents' attitudes toward sanitation and good environmental practices, as well as their inability to pay for proper waste disposal in some cases, were cited by the Waste Management Department as limitations. They used the indiscriminate garbage disposal in the River Aboabo by locals as evidence for their earlier claim. The department listed some of the major difficulties it faced, including a lack of land in slum communities, including Aboabo, to allocate dumpsites and, in some cases, the sale of dumpsites by community chiefs.

4.8.3 Project Undertaken In the Slums

Although an official from the Asokore-Mampong Municipal Assembly (AMMA) claimed that no significant projects were underway, he nevertheless gave us examples of slum development control initiatives that the Kumasi Metropolitan Assembly, which existed before the AMMA's

establishment in 2012, had implemented between 1996 and 2009. The initiatives include Community Infrastructure Upgrading (CIU), the UN-Habitat Slum Upgrading Facility, Urban Environmental, and Sanitation Projects (UESP) I and II, and Urban Environmental and Sanitation Project (UESP) III (SUF). The officer said that among other things, the aforementioned projects concentrated on building public restrooms, roads, and drains, managing waste, providing water and electricity, eradicating slums, and preventing the emergence of new ones. These initiatives improved sanitation and service delivery in Aboabo and other slum areas.

4.8.4 Planned Future Actions

As part of their medium-term development plan, the GWCL intends to extend pipelines to some of the communities. Target communities for the project include Asokore, Atitebi in Mampong, and a few settlements nearby Ayigya. Even though no project is specifically aimed at Aboabo, they intend to implement some projects soon. In communities like Sawaba, Asokore-Mampong (the district capital), and Asawase, the AMMA said they intended to carry out infrastructure development projects. In addition, they said that they had ranked every slum under their control and that they planned to address infrastructure issues about some particular priorities shortly, but they did not provide a specific start date for any such projects.

During the interview, it was discovered that the majority of the institutions interviewed did not indicate any significant collaboration between or among themselves. In addition, slum projects were ignored in some cases due to individual institutional priorities. However, improving slum housing would necessitate a collaborative effort by the various institutional stakeholders. As a result, aligning institutional priorities may become necessary in some cases. This will prevent institutions from delegating their responsibilities to other institutions.

CHAPTER FIVE

CONCLUSION, AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Introduction

This study's objective was to identify feasible financing options for houses in Kumasi's slums. Four areas of inquiry were looked at to reach this goal: the characteristics of housing and living circumstances in slum houses, the identification and study of funding sources for slum house improvement, and the investigation of housing finance choices for slum dwellers. This chapter serves to present the study's findings as well as the numerous suggestions based on them.

5.2 Summary of Results

The following conclusions regarding the research issue were discovered after a comprehensive assessment of the literature and result analysis. The most crucial elements found in the results are listed below.

5.2.1 *Aboabo's Socioeconomic Features*

- The informal sector is where a sizable portion of the respondents work. The majority of responders work in trade and carpentry, among other occupations. Thirty-two (32) respondents did not have jobs, as well.
- In addition, Forty-five percent (45) of the respondents had monthly incomes over GH¢ 300; as a result, a sizeable fraction of the respondents has the financial means to offer substandard housing and other services.

5.2.2 *Finance Options for Housing*

- Personal savings were mostly used to finance construction and house upgrades. The respondents' inability to obtain credit facilities can be blamed for this predicament. According to the report, Sixty-two (62) percent of the respondents utilized personal funds to pay for housing improvements.
- In Aboabo, personal savings are the main source of housing financing. Only four (4) of the respondents could obtain loans from commercial banks. This suggests that residents of

slums are unable to obtain bank loans, which puts financial pressure on landlords. As a result, they are unable to devote a sizable percentage of their salary to housing.

5.3 Available Housing Finance Schemes in Aboabo

The investigation found that there was no housing financing program offered in the neighborhood. However, twenty (20) percent of the respondents were part of savings institutions. Three of the twenty respondents saved with a cooperative society, while seventeen others did so with Susu collectors. However, these savings were primarily intended to supplement family finances in case of emergencies, save for the purchase of home goods, and save for the children's education. According to the study, 98% of the respondents said they were interested in improving their housing. The results of the study showed that the locals were interested in improving housing conditions and their interest in financing their housing development through personal savings (the data available indicates that 75% of the respondents prefer equity financing, which includes personal savings and rent proceeds, while 25% of the respondents would prefer debt financing (loans from banks and co-operative society). This suggests that there is a lot of room for community-based finance initiatives.

5.4 Other Results

Through the institutional interviews conducted as part of the study, certain unintended findings regarding Aboabo were discovered. These comprised:

- According to the Physical Planning Department, Aboabo was initially intended to be a residential area with the correct layout and amenities. The investigation found that traditional authorities, who are the land's custodians, have sold lands to private individuals without considering planning requirements, making it difficult to implement such plans on the ground. This can make it difficult to carry out plans in some cases.
- Because it is a new municipality, Asokore Mampong hasn't undertaken many significant slum improvement projects. The AMMA stated that projects were being carried out in Aboabo at the time by the Kumasi Metropolitan Assembly. The projects include Community Infrastructure Upgrading (CIU), Urban Environmental and Sanitation Projects (UESP) I and II, Urban Environmental and Sanitation Project (UESP) III, and the UN-Habitat Slum Upgrading Facility (SUF), which benefited Aboabo's sanitation and

infrastructure. According to the report, the new Municipality was however working to increase door-to-door rubbish collection to improve sanitation.

- The study also indicated that the Ghana Water Company Limited and the Electricity Company of Ghana regarded slums as temporary settlements; as a result, their policy on temporary settlements restricts them from offering their services (water and electricity supply respectively). On the other hand, it was discovered during the survey that, out of the 90 respondents, ninety-seven (97%) had lived in the neighborhood for more than ten years, and seventy-nine (79%) had inherited their homes. Due to what appears to be an uninterrupted stay in the community by these residents, it is evident from this that they need to modify their policy on temporary settlements.

5.5 Recommendations

The following suggestions are given in light of the study's results and conclusions:

- The study revealed that there is a culture of saving in the neighborhood, as shown by the participation of some residents in neighborhood saving initiatives. Local Susu businesses can band together to create a communal savings plan that will allow the community to raise money for housing renovations. Residents will have more control over financial decisions thanks to this than they would have with separate local savings plans. This action can also draw NGOs, financial institutions, philanthropic groups, and other institutions that are interested since they would rather work with a larger segment of the community than specific Susu companies.
- I suggest regulating local Susu enterprises' behavior (in terms of record keeping, money collection, accountability to the contributors, and payment to contributors) so that locals feel at ease dealing with them. This will encourage savings among the populace. This is significant because residents often have low-income levels, which means that their savings wouldn't be the best if they saved with conventional financial institutions. The members gain from the plan's flexibility because it is more practical. When collecting donations for Susu, for instance, the collectors occasionally move from "store to shop." Members are even permitted to pay as little as GH¢ 1.00.
- The local authorities should coordinate educational initiatives with the Asokore-Mampong Municipal Assembly (AMMA) to inform the residents of Aboabo about concerns with

sanitation and the necessity of abiding by planning restrictions. The educational efforts may be carried out via neighborhood durbars, on radio and television, or through any other suitable media. Additionally, sufficient trash cans must be placed strategically so locals can quickly dispose of their trash. Regular waste removal is necessary to stop residents from pouring their trash down the drains. When completed, this will alter locals' attitudes regarding trash disposal and generally enhance the area's conditions.

- For institutions to provide services to the communities they serve, they need access to those communities' planning schemes. Having dated maps and geographic data can be challenging for them, according to the majority of the institutions who took part in the survey. I propose that funds be set aside in the local assembly's budget for updating geographic and spatial information so that organizations like ECG and the GWCL can quickly implement the provision.
- Regulating and legalizing security of tenure: The Asokore-Mampong Municipal Assembly (AMMA) and the Physical Planning Department (PPD) shall conduct a routine check in the neighborhood to make sure that no one erects an unpermitted structure. Slums cannot be prevented from arising until this happens. Again, when individuals get land from chiefs, they should be required to register their titles rather than keeping their allotment notes. As a result, they will be qualified to receive loans from financial institutions for the improvement of their dwelling situation.
- To enhance and add value to their prior expertise in business and service endeavors, landlords and caretakers should be encouraged to develop their entrepreneurial skills. This will enable them to launch small businesses and raise their capacity for income creation. Additionally, unemployed individuals should be provided with informal training so that they can acquire the skills necessary to find employment in the informal economy, preferably in their start-ups.

5.6 Conclusion

The study's major goal was to identify additional cutting-edge funding options for slum residents and to offer suggestions for how to investigate these financing alternatives to enhance living conditions in slums. Rent profits, individual savings, and loans from cooperative societies are only a few of the funding choices that the studies showed are available in slums. According to the study,

saving was a way of life for the people of Aboabo. However, due to a low salary and a lack of confidence in savings organizations, this habit was restricted.

Aboabo's housing situation requires immediate attention because it is in terrible shape. The community's circumstances are likewise appalling; trash cans are not emptied and are overflowing; gutters are clogged with trash as a result of the community's inadequate refuse collection system; and the roads are in a terrible condition and occasionally inaccessible, especially during heavy downpours.

The study also showed that initiatives like UESP I, UESP II, and SUF were carried out between 1996 and 2009 while Aboabo was governed by the KMA. The quality of life for locals at the time was enhanced by these undertakings. But no such projects have been carried out in the last thirteen years. This might be explained by the fact that funding for these projects came from donor organizations. As a result, it highlights the requirement to identify internal finance options in slums for housing improvement.

It is necessary to strengthen current savings schemes (Susu saving schemes) to increase slum dwellers' access to credit, as well as to establish communal saving schemes by encouraging the merger of the majority of "Susu" organizations. The collective savings plans will provide locals more negotiating power when requesting financing from banking institutions (eg; commercial banks).

I firmly believe that if the aforementioned recommendations are put into practice, housing financing in slums would considerably improve.

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APPENDIX
DEPARTMENT OF PLANNING
KWAME NKRUMAH UNIVERSITY OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY
QUESTIONNAIRES

(This questionnaire is a component of the study "HOUSING FINANCE IN SLUMS IN THE KUMASI METROPOLIS" that will be used to award a Bachelor of Science in Human Settlement Planning. The purpose of the questionnaire is to gather information about the socioeconomic makeup of the neighborhood, the state of the housing market, and the use of financial schemes to enhance neighborhood housing. The information you provide during this interview will be handled with the utmost confidentiality and used only for this study)

QUESTIONNAIRES FOR COMMUNITY MEMBERS

Basic Information:

1. Age of Respondent

2. Length of stay in community years

3. Educational background:

(a) Never attended school { } (b) Primary { } (c) Adult literacy { } (d) Middle/JSS { } (e) Secondary/Vocational/Technical { } (f) Tertiary { }

4. What is your occupation?

(a) Trading { } what type of trade? (b) Teacher { } (c) Caretaker { } (d) Religious Leader { } (e) Messenger { } (f) Security { } (f) Unemployed { } (C) Other { }

Please specify.....

5. Do you own the house you live in?

a. Yes { } b. No { }

6. If yes, how did you get the house?

a. Purchase { } b. Gift/inheritance { } c. Other { } Please specify.....
.....

7. How many bedrooms do you have in your house: { }

8. Do you own the land?

a. Yes { } b. No { }

9. If yes, how did you become the owner?

a. Government { } b. Community { } c. Bought { } d. Family { }

Housing Characteristics

10. What materials were used in building the house?

a. Sandcrete Block { } b. Zinc/Aluminum { } c. Wood { } d. Scrap Material { } e. Landcrete with Bamboo { }

11. What is the current condition of your house?

a. Roof worse { } bad { } regular { } good { } very good { } b. Exterior walls worse { } bad { } regular { } good { } very good { } c. Foundation worse { } bad { } regular { } good { } very good { } d. Floor worse { } bad { } regular { } good { } very good { }

12. How often do you carry out improvements to your house?.....
.....

13. Which parts of your house will you want to improve?
.....

14. Do you regard it as necessary to improve the streets and paths in the community?

Yes { } No { }

Do you have access to:

15. Water in your house?

Yes { } No { }

If yes, is it

(a) Pipe { } (b) borehole { } (c) Well { }

16. If not, how do you get access to water?

.....
.....
.....

17. Electricity?

Yes { } No { }

18. Garbage collection?

Yes { } No { }

19. If no, how do you dispose of the waste?

I. In a hole { } II. Burnt { } III. In water bodies { } IV. In an open space { } V. Dump site { }

Financing Characteristics

20. Have you improved or expanded your house lately?

Yes { } No { }

If the answer is yes, answer Questions 22 and 23

21.If no, why?.....
.....

22. If yes, what did you add to the current structure?

.....

32. What is the main purpose of the saving groups?
.....

33. What does your contribution represent in your monthly income?
.....

34. What is the main source of your income?
.....

35. Do you have other sources of income?

a. Yes { } b. No { }

36. If yes please specify.....
.....

37. Has the Government implemented any project for improving housing in your community?

a. Yes { } b. No { }

38. If yes, what type of project?
.....
.....

39. What are the main monthly expenditure items in your household? (Classify it from 1 to 4, 1 being the most important and 4 being the least important)

a. Food..... c. Water and Electricity..... b. Health and education.....

40. What is the monthly income of your household?

a. Between 101-150 GHC { } b. Between 151-200 GHC { } c. Between 201-250 GHC { } d. More than 251 GHC { }

INSTITUTIONAL INTERVIEW

GHANA WATER COMPANY LIMITED

General information:

Name of respondent:

Position in the organization:

1. What is the type of water service provided in slum communities?

.....
.....

2. What are the main difficulties in providing water to slum communities in Asokore-Mampong Municipality?

.....
.....

3. Do you have any special plans for slum communities in the metropolis?

a. Yes { } b. No { }

4. If yes, what are your potential plans for slum communities?

.....
.....

5. Is there any collaboration with other institutions?

Please, mention them.

.....
.....

INSTITUTIONAL INTERVIEW

ELECTRICITY COMPANY OF GHANA

General information:

Name of respondent:

Position in the organization:

1. What is the type of electricity service provided in slum communities?

.....
.....

3. What are the main difficulties in providing electricity to slum communities in the Asokore Mampong Municipality?

.....
.....
.....

4. Do you have any special plans for slum communities in the municipality?

a. Yes { } b. No { }

5. If yes, what are your potential plans for slum communities?

.....
.....

6. Is there any collaboration with other institutions?

Please, mention them.

.....
.....

INSTITUTIONAL INTERVIEW

PHYSICAL PLANNING DEPARTMENT

General information:

Name of respondent:

Name of the organization

Position in the organization

1. Where are the slum communities in the Asokore-Mampong Municipality?

.....
.....

2. Can you describe the slum situation in the Asokore-Mampong Municipality?

.....
.....

3. Did you plan the areas which have degenerated into slums? Please, indicate how this was done.

.....
.....

4. What are the main difficulties in planning in the Asokore-Mampong Municipality?

Zoning

Development control

Waste management

Traffic management

5. Have you implemented any slum improvement programs? Please describe it.

.....

6. Do you have any special plans for slum communities in the municipality?

a. Yes { } b. No { }

7. If yes, what are your potential plans for slum communities?

.....

8. Is there any collaboration with other institutions?

Please, mention them.

.....

INSTITUTIONAL INTERVIEW

WASTE MANAGEMENT DEPARTMENT (AMMA)

General information:

Name of respondent:

Name of the organization:

Position in the organization:

1. What are the main difficulties in waste management in the Asokore-Mampong Municipality?

.....
.....

2. What type of waste collection service is provided in slum communities?

.....
.....

3. Have you implemented any special waste management programs in the slums? Please describe it.

.....

4. Do you have any special plans for slum communities in the metropolis?

a. Yes { } b. No { }

5. If yes, what are your potential interventions for slum communities?

.....
.....
.....

6. Is there any collaboration with other institutions?

Please, mention them.

.....

COMMUNITY INTERVIEWS

COMMUNITY LEADERS

General information:

Name of the respondent:

Name of the organization:

Position in the organization

1. How are the housing conditions in your community?

.....
.....
.....

2. How is the service provider in your community?

.....
.....

3. What are the major challenges to improving the conditions in your community?

.....
.....
.....

4. Have been implemented any programs have to improve the conditions in your community?

Please describe it.

.....
.....
.....

5. Do you have any financial schemes in your community? Which types?

.....
.....
.....

6. What were the difficulties and the effectiveness of implementing financial schemes in your community?

.....
.....
.....